

D5.1. Multi-criteria assessment framework

María Dolores Gómez-López (UPCT)
Javier Calatrava Leyva (UPCT)
Cristina García Hernández (UPCT)
Xavier Simón Fernández (UVIGO)
Claudia Daniel Escurza González (UVIGO)
David Pérez Neira (UVIGO)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101084084

Funded by
the European Union

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER: 101084084
PROJECT ACRONYM: AGROSUS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The assessment of the sustainability of agricultural systems has been widely studied and has been the subject of numerous methodologies and models. After studying various models, a framework for assessing the sustainability of different agroecological alternatives for weed management based on a multi-criteria model has been chosen. Indicators have been selected in three categories, following the classic assessment theory (environmental, economic and social). The environmental assessment will be carried out by implementing environmental footprint indicators obtained from the life cycle analysis (LCA) methodology. The socio-economic indicators will be taken from the cost-benefit analysis. From the multi-criteria methods studied, the TOPSIS methodology has been selected, which allows us to use data from the selected experimental sites and linguistic assessments of qualitative indicators. Within the chosen MCA framework, the criteria of the multi-criteria model will be the indicators, and the alternatives will be the different management strategies. The result will be a ranking of numerically assessed strategies for each crop and bioregion, which can be implemented with group decision-making tools to obtain conclusions by crop or type of strategy.

Deliverable Number	Work Package / Task
D5.1	WP5 / T5.1
Lead Beneficiary	Deliverable Authors
UPCT	María Dolores Gómez-López Javier Calatrava Leyva Cristina García Hernández
Beneficiaries	Deliverable Co-Authors
UVIGO	Xavier Simón Fernández Claudia Daniel Escurza González David Pérez Neira
Planned Delivery Date	Actual Delivery Date
30/06/2024	28/08/2024

Type of deliverable	R	Document, report	X
	DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
	DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, <i>etc.</i>	
	DATA	Data sets, microdata, <i>etc.</i>	
	OTHER	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, <i>etc.</i>	

Dissemination level	PU	Public, fully open, <i>e.g.</i> , web	X
	SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

INDEX

1. Introduction	4
2. Sustainability assessment	6
2.1. Environmental assessment.....	7
2.2. Economic assessment at farm level	8
2.3. Social assessment	10
3. Frameworks for sustainability assessment for weed management	13
3.1. Frameworks for sustainability assessment.....	13
3.2. SLR for the development of a MCA framework for weed management.....	17
3.2.1. Systematic Literature Review Methodology.....	17
3.2.2. Countries and main crops under study.....	17
3.2.3. Cropping systems and weed management strategies.....	19
3.2.4. Multi-criteria Analysis methods.....	19
3.2.5. Indicators of each dimension	20
4. Multicriteria assessment framework in AGROSUS	21
4.1. Objective.....	21
4.2. The MCD method.....	21
4.3. Crops and bio regions	23
4.4. Criterion selected	24
4.5. Data collection	27
Bibliography	28

TABLES

Table 1. Short- and long-term experimental site selected.	24
Table 2. LCA impact category, indicators and unit.....	27

FIGURES

Figure 1. Agroecological strategies for weed management.	5
Figure 2. Outline of dimensions, themes and subthemes from the guidelines for Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture Systems (SAFA). Source: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) 2014.....	14
Figure 3. Frequency distribution of analysed countries (23 manuscript)	18
Figure 4. Crops analysed in literature	18
Figure 5. Indicators of assessment in literature.....	20
Figure 6. AGROSUS Multicriteria scheme	22
Figure 7. AGROSUS experimental sites selected for multi-criteria assessment.....	24

1. Introduction

Agroecology (AE) is an agricultural approach that integrates the interconnected ecological, sociocultural, technological, economic, and political dimensions of food systems (Sümane et al., 2021). This approach emphasizes the importance of biodiversity, soil health, natural resource conservation, and sustainable development (Wezel and Jauneau, 2011). Agroecology takes a comprehensive view of agriculture and food systems, aiming to transform agroecosystems into sustainable systems through ecological science, innovative agricultural practices, and social movements. It advocates for socially equitable food systems that prioritize food security, local knowledge, and the rights of farmers and rural communities (Wezel et al., 2020).

Agroecology is a transdisciplinary field that transcends the boundaries of traditional disciplines such as agronomy, ecology, sociology, economics, and anthropology. In the agroecological approach (AA), all stakeholders (including researchers, farmers, advisors, businesses, consumers, etc.) collaborate across disciplinary boundaries to understand and address the ecological, social, economic, and political interconnections of agriculture and food systems (Galli et al., 2020). This approach recognizes that these systems are inherently complex and cannot be fully understood or analysed within the limits of a single discipline (Méndez et al., 2015; Nicot et al., 2018; Fernández-González et al., 2021).

In weed management, the adoption of agroecological strategies (AS), which encompass a diverse set of techniques, addresses one of agriculture's main challenges. Weeds cause significant crop losses, representing a considerable cost in time and money for farmers. This issue, along with European Union initiatives such as the Farm to Fork Strategy (European Commission, 2022) aimed at reducing synthetic herbicide use, and the view of AE as a viable transition system for European farms, have increased the popularity of AS in recent years. Therefore, AGROSUS is crucial for sustainable agriculture, as it provides stakeholders with a critical analysis of methods that prioritize ecological balance, biodiversity conservation, and efficient resource use in agricultural practices.

Agroecological strategies offer innovative approaches to weed control, suppressing their growth while enhancing soil health and promoting biodiversity. These AS can be divided into categories (Figure 1) such as cultural, mechanical/physical, or biological/biotechnological. By promoting a diverse agroecosystem, these strategies naturally reduce the risks associated with pests and pathogens, decrease reliance on synthetic pesticides, and foster long-term resilience.

In Europe, non-organic and pesticide-free production systems are also emerging as a novel approach to agricultural pest management. This approach offers a "third way" between conventional and organic practices, with lower adoption barriers and greater flexibility than traditional organic agriculture (Finger and Mohring, 2024). Since soil health is the foundation of agricultural productivity, incorporating agroecological principles into soil management strategies is crucial for enhancing soil fertility, structure, and microbial diversity. Ultimately, this review highlights the importance of the implementation of AS in addressing the challenges of modern agriculture, providing sustainable solutions for weed management while promoting the health and resilience of agroecosystems.

Figure 1. Examples of agroecological strategies for weed management.

The success of the AS often hinges on their tailored application to specific crops and regional contexts. Current AA for weed management underscore their significance in fostering sustainable agricultural systems (Gliessman, 2016). Agroecological strategies provide effective and environmentally friendly solutions for weed control, reducing reliance on synthetic herbicides and minimizing environmental impact (Hawkesford et al., 2013). Moreover, the integration of digital technologies enhances the precision and efficiency of these practices, optimizing resource use and further mitigating environmental effects (Zhang et al., 2021).

It is also essential to consider the variation in AS based on crop types and regional conditions (Gliessman, 2016). The critical role of agroecology in addressing weed management challenges while promoting sustainability in European agriculture has been well-documented (Wezel et al., 2020). By examining sustainability indicators, we can gain valuable insights into the practical applications and future directions of weed management AS, selecting the most effective options for each specific problem (Altieri, 1999; Hawkesford et al., 2013).

In sum, the aim of this deliverable is to review the selected environmental-socio-economic approaches to evaluate agroecological management practices that aim to weed management. We discuss the applicability of these approaches, their pros and cons and possible links and

synergies between approaches. We review the key empirical studies using these approaches. Based on the literature reviews we build a common integrated framework in AGROSUS WP5 that will serve to assess the Agroecological Strategies (AS) for weed management. Different theoretical strands lay the foundation of this integrated framework. This assessment framework itself provides a combination of methodologies which aims to pursue coherent data collection in the different study cases, and allows for comparative analysis.

A multi-criteria assessment (MCA) framework has been designed in AGROSUS for studying the socio-economic and environmental impact and comparison of conventional and AE weed management strategies, which is explained in this deliverable.

2. Sustainability assessment

In agricultural systems, sustainability implies the production of sufficient quantities of high-quality food to feed the population without damaging the environment, preserving natural resources and biodiversity, maintaining farmers' incomes and quality of life, and contributing to rural development and the economy of the agricultural sector. Researchers define AE as an interdisciplinary field aimed at solving essential problems about the interactions between nature and humans.

The Brundtland report defines *sustainability* as: “Development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (WCED, 1987). The FAO’s elaborated definition of *sustainable agriculture* is: “the management and conservation of the natural resource base, and the orientation of technological change in such a manner as to ensure the attainment of continued satisfaction of human needs for present and future generations. Sustainable agriculture conserves land, water, and plant and animal genetic resources is environmentally non-degrading, technically appropriate, economically viable and socially acceptable” (FAO, 1988).

While *sustainability assessment* originally mainly focused on the environmental impacts of farming (e.g. van der Werf and Petit, 2002; Payraudeau and van der Werf, 2005), in recent decades it has been acknowledged that the environmental, social and economic dimension of sustainability need to be evaluated simultaneously in an integrated assessment (Hardi and Zdan, 1997; Kates et al., 2005; Hurni and Osman-Elasha, 2009; FAO, 2013; Schindler et al., 2015). This allows to reveal trade-offs and synergies within the system. Sustainability assessment is “conducted for supporting decision-making and policy in a broad environmental, economic and social context, and transcends a purely technical/scientific evaluation” (Sala et al., 2015). It aims to direct decision-making towards sustainability (Pope et al., 2017).

In AGROSUS the focus is on decision-making by farmers, more specifically on decisions about implementing agroecological practices to weed management. Sustainability assessment will provide insights on the impact of these practices on overall farm sustainability, i.e. on the different dimensions of sustainability and the trade-offs between them. Sustainability assessment thus provides support to direct farm management towards more sustainability.

Therefore, although they can be evaluated separately, as we see below, they must subsequently

be implemented in an integrated tool and in a joint framework.

2.1. Environmental assessment

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) covers environmental assessment and includes the full production chain. It is defined by the European Commission as an internationally standardized scientific methodology aimed to study the environmental impacts of goods and services. It takes into account the full cycle from the raw material extraction, through transformation, manufacturing, transport, use, and end-of-life.

The relevant emissions, energy, and material resources related to human activities are quantified in every stage and then classified into impact categories by a Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) method (ILCD 2010). These impact categories can describe midpoint (climate change, ozone depletion, etc.) or endpoint consequences (loss of biodiversity, damage to human health). In both cases, the interpretation of the assessment must follow a multi-criteria and multi-category baseline in order to avoid burden shifting when studying the consequences of innovative goods, services or management approaches.

Nowadays, the indispensable framework for LCA is provided by the ISO 14040 and 14044, although several standardization and harmonization initiatives have been developed or are under current development.

The ISO standards 14040 and 14044 do not recommend using any specific LCIA method, but according to the ISO 14044, the selected impact categories “shall reflect a comprehensive set of environmental issues related to the product system being studied, taking the goal and scope into consideration” (Hauschild, 2018). However, some organizations do provide more specific recommendations. For example, the European Commission has published recommendations for midpoint and endpoint impact categories by evaluating all relevant existing approaches per impact category, leading to the recommendation of the best available approach and the development of the International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) method (ILCD, 2010). The method includes 12 midpoint impact categories (climate change, stratospheric ozone depletion, human toxicity, particulate matter formation, ionizing radiation, photochemical ozone formation, acidification, eutrophication, ecotoxicity, land use, water use, and resource use), and three endpoint areas of protection (human health, natural environment, and natural resources).

LCA methodologies and impact assessment methods have evolved significantly in the last 50 years. In the 1970s the efforts of impact assessment on the food sector were firstly focused in reducing the impacts associated to packaging but, after the 1990s, full production processes were included in a full assessment, first called Resource and Environmental Profile Analyses. The emergence of LCA methodologies (Gaillard, 2005) and environmental policies have pushed the development of environmental impact assessments of food supply chains with different purposes: R&D and business strategy support, eco-design of products and processes, divulgation, support to environmental innovative solutions, communication among stakeholders, labelling or environmental product declarations (EPDs), etc. Ecolabels based on LCA for food products exist (such as Green Crane), although the European Commission did not create an EU Ecolabel for food and feed products due to difficulty to measure the impacts in the production stage, the variability of results due to region, technology and product, the high cost associated to the development of reliable LCA on agriculture products, etc. (Oakdene Hollins, 2011). The development of consistent

methodologies for agriculture products would lead to use of LCA results to support policy making in the sector.

In private companies, the use of LCA is becoming more popular since Unilever created a software for the LCA of margarine production (Bloemhof-Ruwaard et al., 1995). Since then, the development of specific software for LCA (such as SimaPro or Gabi) has allowed the application of LCA in the decision-making phase of private institutions and researchers from every life cycle stage (from crop management to end-of-life of packaging, for example). More recently, LCA has been also used to develop informing and design tools, such as the GEOFootPrint tool (GEOFootPrint, 2020) that displays the regionalized environmental impacts, and its sources of several crops.

As comparability is only possible when the same methods and methodologies have been used, harmonization is a requirement for the applications that support policy and decision-making. Methodologies, impact assessment methods, and databases have been developed in parallel to assess the environmental impacts of the agriculture sector (SALCA, MEXA LCA, Agrybalise), and to ease the access to reliable data. The newest guidelines are based on the experience gained during the years of application of previous guidelines. These guidelines try to establish common approaches to deal with specific agriculture aspects, such as the pesticides and fertilizers modelling, the CO₂ uptake, the degradation of soil, or the impacts derived from land use change. Other issues, such as impacts on ecosystem services, are less developed and are being currently assessed to include them in future LCA methodologies (Liu et al., 2019).

Harmonizing the methodologies is not easy, as they are in constant development, and the goal and scope of LCAs for agricultural products can vary depending on the sub-sector and product type. Forestry, horticulture, bio-economy (bio-energy, bio-based materials, etc.) or crop production need different approaches to carry out the LCA given the huge differences among these sub-sectors. In consequence, the development of Product Category Rules (PCRs) for specific products is one approach proposed by the European Commission to enable reliable comparison of results among products and ease the communication of results. In PCRs, the system boundaries and the functional unit (FU) is defined for a specific product, narrowing down the options for the selection of the FU, given that it can be defined according to land management criteria (ha*year, with the goal to minimize land use intensity), productivity (MJ or kg, to enhance eco-efficiency), or financial criteria (monetary units to optimize economic efficiency) (Nemecek, 2013).

Farmers managing weeds should build the habits of collaborating with LCA practitioners to build and update data inventories in a practical way to provide meaningful and high-quality data without compromising their time resources. By other hand, the results and conclusions obtained from LCA studies developed by different authors are only comparable if the same assessment methods and methodologies have been used, thus harmonization is a key step towards the applicability of LCA in all types of management frameworks, including weed management.

2.2. Economic assessment at farm level

The adoption of new farming practices is a complex process driven by numerous factors (environmental, social, institutional, behavioural, economic). Of special relevance are farmer's awareness, knowledge and perception about the feasibility of the technology to be adopted, and its potential to contribute to the fulfilment of farmer's objectives (Pannell, 1999).

Consequently, profitability is a key aspect of the adoption decision process. Demonstrating the economic implications of adopting more sustainable farming practices requires assessing whether the costs derived from such adoption can be compensated by their benefits.

The farm level economic analysis of weed management practices aims to assess the impact of the practices on crop profitability under various pedoclimatic conditions, paying special attention to the reduction in the use of herbicides, but also mineral fertilizers and pesticides, going along with practices. The purpose is to provide impact estimates resulting from the analysed practices on crop profitability (changes in input use intensity and crop yield).

Consequently, the basis for such analysis would be the experimental activities regarding farming practices, input use and crop production, to be able to assess and to demonstrate how the new agroecological farming practices can contribute to revenues and production costs. However, some costs, such as machinery depreciation, are usually specific to each farm, and can be subjected to a large variability. In principle, the farming practices to be field-tested are not expected to significantly affect indirect production costs. For this reason, the analysis at the farm level can be limited at the crop level, analysing the impact of the AE weed management enhancing management practices on crop's gross margin. Gross margin (GM) is defined as the difference between revenue (value of production plus subsidies) and all variable costs directly attributable to each crop (Turner and Taylor, 1998).

The assessment of the profitability for farmers of alternative agricultural practices or technologies can be approached in different ways, usually contingent on the research's objectives and data availability. In any case, assessing the relative profitability of different agricultural practices/technologies requires some definition of the production and cost functions, i.e., the impact of the analysed practice/technology on production (changes in crop yield and/or quality) and/or production costs (changes in input use intensity).

A first approach would rely on the econometric analysis of farm data. Data from a sample of farms can be used to estimate economic indicators (e.g., production/cost/revenues/profit functions) by relating those with technological choices (e.g., farming practices or agricultural technologies implemented in the farms). While having the advantage of relying on the use of real data from commercial farms, this approach requires that the farming practices/technologies analysed must be already implemented in a sufficient number of the surveyed farms, which reduces the applicability of econometric tools in the case of new practices/technologies that have not, or barely have, being implemented on commercial farms.

Additionally, farming practices/technologies whose profitability is analysed are usually defined in a very generic way (e.g., mechanical versus chemical weed control, minimum tillage versus conventional tillage, organic farming versus conventional farming), without entering in detail regarding how each practice is being implemented (i.e., by differentiating between different tillage intensities or herbicide dosage, etc). This could be solved by collecting more detailed information on how each farmer is implementing a given farming practice/technology.

The econometric analysis of farm survey data has been used in empirical studies in the cases of established farming methods. For example, Rasul and Thapa (2004) used data from a sample of farms to compute profitability indicators for both conventional and organic production in Bangladeshi agricultural systems, while Schimmelpfennig (2018) assessed the impact of precision agriculture techniques on the profitability of US soybean cropping using official survey data. A vast literature has also used this approach to analyse technical and cost efficiency in

agricultural production and to compare different agricultural technologies. For example, Mayen et al. (2010) compared technical efficiency of both conventional and organic production systems in dairy farms of the US, while Oumer et al. (2020) compared the cost-efficiency of sustainable farming practices in Ethiopian corn farms.

A second approach for economic assessment of farming practices and technologies is combining partial budgeting with experimental field data. Partial crop budgeting consists of calculating the effect on profitability of changes in the crop production process, either in terms of changes in production costs, crops yields or farm prices. This approach is more suitable when the focus of the analysis is more detailed or when the analysed technologies are in an experimental phase and are not implemented in commercial farms, as it is the case in the AGROSUS project. The basis for any partial budgeting is the elaboration of a detailed technical-economic characterisation of the crop production process in terms of farming practices, crop yields, input use, and production costs, from which detailed budgets can be built to integrate changes in input use and output for competing practices.

Partial crop budgeting is the most common tool used to analyse the profitability of alternative agricultural practices and technologies (Swinton and Lowenberg-DeBoer, 1998). A vast number of applications of partial crop budgeting based on experimental field data already exists. To name a few studies with relation to the type of farming practices of weed control, considered in AGROSUS: Jackson et al. (2004) assessed the impact of tillage and organic matter management alternatives on the profitability of Californian horticulture; Sartori et al. (2005) assessed the impact of crop rotations and organic farming on the production costs of several arable crops in Italy; Aryal et al. (2015) analysed the impact of zero tillage on the profitability of wheat production in NW India; Adamtey et al. (2016) compared the effect of both conventional and organic production systems on input productivity and profitability in Kenya corn production; Yost et al. (2019) assessed the long-term profitability of precision agriculture techniques and soil conservation practices in corn-soybean rotations in Missouri; and Kumar et al. (2018) analysed the impact of sustainable farming practices, related to tillage, crop diversification, and precision agriculture techniques on the productivity and profitability of Indian cereal production.

Finally, a related alternative approach is bio-economic modelling, which rely both on crop growth models to produce computer simulations of the biophysical performance of alternative farming practices/technologies, and economic modelling (from partial crop budgeting to agro-economic models) to assess their relative profitability. This was used for example, by Sattler et al. (2020) to analyse the impact of alternative farming practices (including tillage, fertilization, weed and pest control and harvesting) on the profitability of relevant crops in Germany.

2.3. Social assessment

Farmers are constantly exploring new ways to improve their agricultural practices. The decision to adopt new farming techniques, however, is not just a straightforward economic calculation, but involves a comprehensive evaluation of potential costs and benefits, which affect the environment, the economy, and, most importantly, the society. This is where the Social Cost-Benefit Analysis (SCBA) comes into play, offering a holistic framework for understanding the broader impacts of these changes (Boardman et al., 2018).

Imagine a small farming community considering the adoption of conservation agriculture—a method that emphasizes minimal soil disturbance, crop rotation, and cover cropping. At first glance, the benefits seem obvious: healthier soils, increased biodiversity, and potential yield

improvements over time. But what about the costs? Farmers must invest in new equipment, undergo training to learn the new practices, and potentially face a temporary dip in crop yields due to soil and spontaneous flora transitions (Lal, 2004; Pretty et al., 2006).

The SCBA begins by identifying all possible costs and benefits of adopting these practices. It looks beyond the direct financial costs, such as buying new machinery, and considers indirect social costs, like the impact on local employment or changes to traditional farming methods that have been passed down through generations (Pearce et al., 2006).

To get a full picture, SCBA assigns monetary values to these costs and benefits whenever possible. This includes not only market prices but also less tangible factors. For instance, how do you quantify the benefit of improving soil health or reducing weeds, or the cost of losing cultural traditions tied to older farming methods? These are critical questions that SCBA seeks to address by using both quantitative and qualitative assessments (Hanley and Spash, 1993).

An essential part of this analysis is understanding the time horizon—how these costs and benefits will play out over years or even decades. Conservation agriculture might have higher upfront costs, but it promises long-term benefits such as increased resilience to climate change and reduced reliance on chemical inputs. To accurately compare these future benefits to current costs, SCBA employs a discount rate, which helps determine the present value of future gains and losses (Gittinger, 1982).

The future is always uncertain, and agriculture is particularly susceptible to variability in weather, market conditions, and technological advancements. SCBA tackles this uncertainty by conducting sensitivity analyses, which test how changes in key assumptions affect outcomes. For instance, what if climate change accelerates, and the benefits of conservation agriculture are realized sooner than expected? Or what if market prices for crops fluctuate significantly? (Pannell, 2003).

By exploring various scenarios, SCBA provides farmers and policymakers with a clearer understanding of the potential risks and rewards, helping them to make informed decisions that are resilient to change (Pearce et al., 2006).

Taking the case of agroecological farming practices, which have gained popularity for their promise of sustainability, AS avoid the use of synthetic pesticides and fertilizers, relying instead on natural inputs to maintain soil fertility and pest control, which often leads to higher labour costs and potential yield reductions, especially in the initial years. However, these costs are counterbalanced by premium prices for organic products, improved environmental outcomes, and enhanced biodiversity (Reganold and Wachter, 2016).

A social cost-benefit analysis of agroecological farming reveals that, over time, the environmental and social benefits, such as healthier ecosystems and increased social capital in rural areas, often outweigh the economic costs. Farmers who adopt agroecological practices frequently report not only higher profits from premium markets but also a sense of contributing to broader societal goals of health and sustainability (Crowder and Reganold, 2015).

Another compelling example is agroforestry, which integrates trees into agricultural landscapes. Initially, farmers face costs related to planting and maintaining trees. However, agroforestry systems can provide diversified income sources, improved water management, and enhanced resilience against climate extremes. SCBA demonstrates that the long-term benefits of agroforestry, including improved livelihoods and ecosystem services, make it an attractive

option for many farmers (Jose, 2009).

Ultimately, the social cost-benefit analysis of adopting agricultural practices provides a nuanced perspective that goes beyond traditional economic evaluations. It captures the interconnectedness of economic, social, and environmental factors, highlighting the need for balanced and informed decision-making (Vanclay, 2003).

By considering the diverse impacts of new farming techniques, SCBA helps ensure that agricultural practices not only boost productivity but also contribute positively to community well-being and environmental sustainability. As farmers and policymakers navigate the challenges of modern agriculture, SCBA serves as a vital tool for guiding decisions that will shape the future of farming and the world, we live in.

In the literature we can find some examples of analysis cost-benefit of weed management so in the adoption of Integrated Weed Management (IWM). Pannell (2003) showed that farmers dealing with herbicide-resistant weed populations have increasingly turned to Integrated Weed Management (IWM). IWM combines cultural, mechanical, and chemical methods to control weeds. The analysis included the costs of adopting new technologies, such as precision agriculture tools for better weed monitoring, and the cost of training farmers on new practices. Benefits were assessed in terms of improved crop yields, reduced reliance on herbicides, and decreased incidence of herbicide-resistant weeds. Environmental benefits, such as reduced chemical runoff and improved soil health, were also considered. The SCBA showed that while the initial investment in IWM practices was high, the long-term benefits, including reduced herbicide use and environmental improvements, outweighed the costs. This led to a more sustainable approach to weed management.

In California, Pretty et al. (2006) found that cover crops have been used as a strategy for weed management in vegetable production systems. Cover crops help suppress weed growth and improve soil health. The costs analysed included the expenses for purchasing and planting cover crops, as well as any additional labour required. Benefits were evaluated in terms of reduced weed density, improved soil fertility, and potential increases in crop yields. Environmental benefits, such as reduced soil erosion and enhanced water retention, were also factored into the analysis (Jose, 2009). The SCBA indicated that the benefits of using cover crops—such as improved soil health and reduced weed pressure—outweighed the costs. This approach not only provided economic advantages through higher yields but also contributed positively to environmental sustainability.

Other example is the mechanical Weed Control in Organic Farming in Europe described in Jose (2009). Organic farmers in Europe have increasingly adopted mechanical weed control methods, such as weed harrows and inter-row cultivators, to manage weeds without synthetic herbicides. The analysis included costs for purchasing mechanical weeding equipment and the additional labour required for its operation. Benefits were assessed in terms of reduced herbicide use, improved soil health, and potentially higher market prices for organic produce. The SCBA also considered the social benefits of reduced exposure to harmful chemicals and improved worker health (Vanclay, 2003). The SCBA demonstrated that while mechanical weed control required significant upfront investment and labour, the long-term benefits—including improved soil health, reduced chemical exposure, and access to premium organic markets—provided a favourable cost-benefit ratio (Jose, 2009)

3. Frameworks for sustainability assessment for weed management

3.1. Frameworks for sustainability assessment

Sustainability assessment itself encompasses different dimensions and must be based on a solid framework (Sala et al., 2015). For all these reasons, the FAO defined a tool for the Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agricultural Systems (SAFA) in 2013 (FAO, 2013). This tool is based on defining four dimensions of sustainability, beyond the three classic ones proposed in numerous works: environmental integrity, economic resilience and social well-being, plus the recently introduced "good governance". SAFA has a hierarchical structure that groups the indicators into dimensions (4), themes (21) and sub-themes (58) (Figure 2). This tool helps to establish the limits of the system and to select objectives, practices or performance indicators based on qualitative or quantitative information. However, there are indicators that need adaptation and the indicators related to the socioeconomic part are not flexible for the different systems (Alaoui et al., 2022).

Establishing the system boundaries should be one of the first steps in evaluating, and will also help us to compare goods, services and projects (FAO, 2013; Schader et al., 2014). In agriculture, establishing the farm gate as the boundary is usually the most advisable, since the direct effects of performance are evaluated, as well as the indirect effects caused by agricultural inputs. In this case, the effects beyond the farm gate are not considered, which may include aspects such as processing, handling or transport, which seems logical, since it presents great variability and is beyond the reach of the farmer, in most cases.

Next, defining the conceptual framework should be the next step, choosing a single tool or a combination of several, thus obtaining a monitoring of the sustainability of our system (Gasparatos and Scolobig, 2012).

The tools described can be presented in the form of software, applications or in a disaggregated form to be implemented later, but all of them have to be based on indicators. Indicators are variables that give information on parameters that are difficult to measure directly. They measure performance or reflect changes in activities, projects or programs. These indicators must be based on easy-to-use measures and implemented in tools or a set of models relatively simple for farmers, because they simplify the complex system, inform, and encourage decision-making (Girardin et al., 1999; Hák et al., 2007; UNAIDS, 2010).

From the bibliography, three types of indicators can be clearly distinguished: (1) objective-based indicators, which evaluate whether the proposed plans or policies have been achieved; (2) practice-based indicators, which evaluate agricultural practices or the technical means used; and (3) Performance-based indicators, also called outcome-based or result-oriented, which are used to assess the impact of practices (FAO, 2013: 56-59). Therefore, the type of indicator used as well as the complexity of the sustainability assessment tools is decisive when it comes to their use by farmers and decision-makers (Coteur et al., 2020).

Figure 2. Outline of dimensions, themes and subthemes from the guidelines for Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture Systems (SAFA). Source: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) 2014

For all the above reasons, the so-called multi-criteria models could be a strategy to consider as tools to assess sustainability, especially in the three dimensions, environmental, economic, and social. Multi-criteria models allow mathematically combining the different magnitudes and applying a weight of importance to each of them, depending on the model to be treated.

Although there is a multitude of multi-criteria methodologies for sustainability assessment, in general they all follow 4 main steps: (i) definition of assessment objectives; (ii) definition and description of assessed systems; (iii) selection of criteria and indicators and estimation of parameters based on calculations or measurements; and (iv) final assessment, which may combine information from several indicators and use thresholds or reference values to determine the viability of the system (Deytieux et al., 2016).

Integrated sustainability assessment tools (ISATs) (or multi-criteria assessments) have been

developed and used for many purposes, including monitoring, reporting (obligatory), communication to customers (non-committal), farm or product certification, landscape planning, farm advice or development, policy advice, and research (Schader et al., 2014; Wustenberghs et al., 2015). At the farm level, ISATs have been used, among others, to benchmark farms worldwide and across farming sectors, to compare production systems (e.g., organic vs. conventional), to support multi-actor decision making, and to design innovative production systems (Schader et al., 2016; Gésan-Guiziou, 2020). Most comprehensive ISATs do evaluate soil quality as a theme within the environmental dimension, e.g., in MOTIFS (Meul et al., 2008), RISE (Häni et al., 2003, Grenz et al., 2009), PGTTool (Gerrard et al., 2012), SAFA (FAO, 2013) or SMART (Schader et al., 2016).

Several ISATs, however, do aim at evaluating changes in farming practices. MASC, for example, is a qualitative multi-attribute decision model for *ex ante* assessment of the sustainability of changes in cropping systems. The model compares potential alternative cropping systems to the prevailing system. It encompasses three farm sustainability dimensions and can incorporate informal knowledge into the assessment, via the use of qualitative information (Sadok et al., 2009). MASC has been used to assess innovative cropping systems aiming to mitigate climate change (Craheix et al., 2014) and to evaluate the sustainability of conservation agriculture at the cropping system level (Craheix et al., 2016). Built on the same software basis as MASC, also DEXiPM (DEXi Pest Management) was developed for *ex ante* assessment of cropping systems' sustainability, particularly integrated crop management systems with a limited use of pesticides (Pelzer et al., 2012). Originally designed for arable crops, DEXiPM has also been adapted for use in field vegetables, grapevines and pome fruit orchards (Angevin et al., 2017; Caffi et al., 2017), while it can now also be implemented *ex post*.

locola et al. (2020) present a multi-criteria assessment able to assess rotations over several years. Their indicator set was designed to be sensitive to the holistic sustainability performance of crop diversification strategies. Thus, to adequately represent trade-offs (e.g. enhanced ecosystem services countered with less profitability or increased costs of new practices) and carry-over effects within innovative rotations (e.g. reduced need for nitrogen fertilization after a leguminous crop, weed suppression in the succeeding crops after a ley). This ISAT was developed for and is being used in the DiverIMPACTS project (H2020 n°727482). It is implemented for critical *ex post* diagnosis of existing systems and for *ex ante* assessment of innovative cropping system scenarios. The assessment outcomes have allowed local actors to reflect on the effects generated by the new practices implemented.

An interesting innovation in the implementation of ISATs was introduced by Winter et al. (2020). Instead of assessing existing farms, as previously done, they used a typical farms approach. The typical farm is defined as the farm type that represents the mode of the distribution of farms, i.e. the farm that can be found most often on the ground. It thus differs from the average farm that depicts the mean of all farms and which rarely actually exists on the ground. Constructing typical farms is started from literature and then supplemented and verified by experts. In their sustainability assessment of coffee production systems Winter et al. (2020) applied the SMART-Farm Tool (Schader et al., 2016) to typical farms. SMART represents an operationalization of the SAFA framework (FAO, 2013), described in section 2.4. The data for the typical farm assessment was also collected through expert interviews. However, they encountered some difficulties when discussing the SMART indicators for the typical systems. Experts occasionally found it difficult to give an estimation in such detail as required by the SMART-Farm Tool. Winter et al. (2020) therefore suggests using more general indicators for future expert judgements.

Nevertheless, the typical farm approach seems interesting to assess sustainability in projects where the number of real farm cases is limited, such as in AGROSUS.

There are other frameworks worthy of mention:

The SAFE (Sustainability Assessment of Food Agriculture) framework is a hierarchical framework that can use three spatial levels (plot, farm and landscape) that provides an overview of landscape sustainability initiatives. It has a multifunctional character that encompasses the three pillars of sustainability and is composed of specific indicators and reference values that are the end products of the framework. The framework is limited to agricultural production activities and therefore does not lead to double counting. Because of this, it excludes external impacts such as transport, processing or packaging of products, as well as upstream activities of input manufacturing or extraction of raw materials (Van Cauwenbergh et al., 2007).

The Indigo methodology establishes a set of sustainability indicators that has served as a reference for the construction of indicators, methodologies and models today (Craheix et al., 2016). These are predictive indicators based on operational models that assess the effect of agricultural practices in interaction with soil and climate. One advantage is that they are adaptable to available scientific knowledge and to all agricultural productions, but they use a restricted number of input data and are individually of low predictive quality (Thiollet-Scholtus and Bockstaller, 2015).

The RISE (Response-inducing sustainability evaluation) framework includes 50 categorised qualitative indicators covering the 3 aspects of sustainability, organised hierarchically through 32 input criteria. Although it shows potential for integrating the social dimension, the inclusion of experts would be necessary (Alaoui et al., 2022).

The LADA (Land Degradation Assessment in Drylands) framework, also proposed by FAO, is used to assess and quantify the nature, severity, impact and extent of land degradation through indicators, pressures and drivers of change. The social dimension is represented by pressures on resources. Data is collected through direct field measurements, surveys and databases such as digital maps. In addition, it has climate components and data for the assessment of external climate phenomena. However, it is a framework limited to people with multi-sectoral expertise and some authors claim that it uses models that are too general (Alaoui et al., 2022).

The PG (Public goods) framework is a framework developed in the UK for the assessment of agricultural public goods. It uses 11 public goods collected through qualitative and quantitative data questionnaires. It is an easy to apply framework, but its input data are not very specific (Alaoui et al., 2022).

Other less common frameworks are MESMIS or SALT (Calleros-Islas, 2019). The tool that allows sustainability to be assessed through a multi-criteria analysis and is governed by the principles of agroecology, although the complexity of its basic attributes makes the definition of indicators a difficult task. It incorporates cost-benefit and stakeholder analyses. It is outdated (Van Cauwenbergh et al., 2007). On the other hand, SALT divides sustainability into 4 parts (social, institutional, economic and environmental) and is applied at the local scale (Calleros-Islas, 2019).

As we can see many farm level sustainability assessment tools have been developed, reflecting the variety and complexity of agricultural systems and the variety of sustainability perceptions. Classifying SATs according to their complexity and the steps in the farmer's strategic decision-making process they support, revealed that some tools provide only a weak link to the farmer's

decision-making process.

Hence, for a SAT to incite action towards sustainable farm development it should be farm(er) focused. Moreover, the assessment process should also include support beyond the mere implementation of the tool, i.e. in interpreting the SATs results, developing improvement strategies and implementing them. Interaction between farmers, advisors and experts in all steps and even in the development of the SAT has great added value (Coteur et al., 2020).

Because of this, sustainability assessment requires the use of multi-criteria approaches considering various components of sustainability (Cui et al., 2021; Deytieux et al., 2016), as we propose.

3.2. SLR for the development of an MCA framework for weed management

3.2.1. Systematic Literature Review Methodology

The methodology used to test the initial hypothesis is a Systematic Literature Review (SLR). SLR is characterized by being an exhaustive and meticulous method designed to identify the most relevant works on a specific topic. These works are in the main bibliographic databases and subjected to a predefined and explicit analysis to avoid research biases (Sáenz, 2001).

The search string used was:

"Weed*" and ("multi-criteria assessment" or "multi criteria assessment" or "multicriteria assessment" or "multicriteria evaluation" or "multi-criteria evaluation" or "multi criteria evaluation")

It was entered into Web of Science and Scopus, yielding 50 results. After deleting duplicated and rejected documents, 18 papers from the SLR and 3 additional papers were reviewed. The acceptance criteria for the documents were: a) be a scientific article, b) be an empirical investigation, c) evaluate agronomic practices that serve to control weeds, d) analyse 2 or more dimensions of the MCA, e) be written in English or Spanish.

The 21 accepted articles were submitted to the following data extraction form: a) country, b) type of crop, c) type of cropping system, d) production method, e) weeds present in the crops, f) weed treatment, g) if they make a comparison between methods, h) MCA tool, g) objectives, h) scope, i) main results, j) agronomic, environmental, economic and social indicators, k) agronomic, environmental, economic and social results.

3.2.2. Countries and main crops under study

Regarding the countries most frequently analysed in the literature, France stands out with 13 studies, distributed among 3 of the 4 French bioregions (Atlantic, Continental and Mediterranean). This is followed by Guadeloupe and Martinique, a French overseas region, and Laos, both with 3 papers. In the first region, citrus orchards are analysed, while in the second, maize cultivation is evaluated.

Figure 3. Frequency distribution of analysed countries (23 manuscript)

Maize is the main crop receiving the most attention, followed by wheat. This is because these are two of the most widespread monocultures in France. As one of the main objectives of these studies is the substitution of monocultures, we find that, within the diversification strategy, crops such as barley and rapeseed are often planted.

Figure 4. Crops analysed in literature

3.2.3. Cropping systems and weed management strategies

Almost all research compares conventional cropping systems, in which herbicide use is usually high and is the main element of weed control, with alternative systems. Some studies consider their methods as agroecological, with Conservation Agriculture (CA) being highlighted here. The three pillars of CA are: crop diversification, maximizing the duration of soil cover with living plants or mulch, and reducing or ceasing tillage (Adeux et al., 2022; Craheix et al., 2016). Other systems practiced are Integrated Weed Management (IWM) or Integrated Pest Management (IPM) (Petit et al., 2015). The most frequently used alternative practices are intercropping, diversification of crop rotation and cover crops (Jannoyer, Le Bellec, et al., 2011; Jannoyer, Malézieux, et al., 2011; Le Bellec et al., 2012), which correspond to the cultural strategies implemented by AGROSUS. Other strategies employed are reduced tillage, false seed beds, doubling sowing rate (Leclere et al., 2019), increasing the number of shallow tillage operations with mechanical weeding and later sowing date.

3.2.4. Multi-criteria Analysis methods

There are 3 fundamental issues to consider when we wish to carry out a multi-criteria analysis. The first is the definition of this, as we must ask ourselves whether the MCA includes the weighting of the criteria or whether it is simply a matter of showing the evolution/change in the values of the indicators of several dimensions analysed simultaneously. If we want to incorporate our decisions into the process, we must determine the weight we give to each dimension and, within this, to each indicator. This is where the second key point comes in: choosing the software, the model and the method of calculating the indicators. The only software mentioned in the documents is DEXi (Lairez et al., 2023), specifically the DEXiPM (Pest Management) version (Cavan et al., 2023; Viguier et al., 2021), a program developed by researchers in Slovenia¹. This software assists in decision-making processes that involve multiple attributes. DEXiPM is a decision tree designed for conducting ex ante sustainability assessments of innovative cropping systems aimed at reducing pesticide use. Given the limited availability of experimental results on these systems, the tree's leaves represent basic qualitative criteria, which describe the farming practices and the context of the cropping system. These fundamental criteria are progressively aggregated, culminating in three final scores that reflect the social, environmental, and economic dimensions of sustainability. Although this search did not find any articles using DEXi for ex post evaluations, a broader search on MCA applied to cropping systems did find adaptations, so it would be possible to evaluate the project's experiments using this software.

Concerning the models, we find that only one is mentioned: MASC (Multi-attribute Assessment of the Sustainability of Cropping systems) (Sadok et al., 2009), specifically MASC 2.0, powered by DEXi (Alletto et al., 2022). It combines a hierarchical multi-attribute decision model and an expert system. A total of 39 criteria are distributed across the three key sustainability elements—environment, economics, and social concerns—within a hierarchical structure that assigns their weight in the final assessment.

The remaining analyses are performed under different methods: showing the indicators before and after implementing the alternative practices, calculating the percentages of change and rating them or normalizing the values of the indicators between 0 and 1 and aggregating them through

a geometric mean (Lairez, Jourdain, et al., 2023). Other methods found in the literature for MCA on crops (without restricting it to weeds) include Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), Fuzzy Logic, Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (FAHP), PROMETHEE, TOPSIS, IDEA, weighted sum and weighted product.

3.2.5. Selected indicators of each dimension

The following Figure 5 shows all the indicators mentioned in the articles included in the SLR.

Figure 5. Indicators of assessment in literature

When selecting the indicators for the evaluation of the AS implemented in the AGROSUS project, it would be important to consider the type of strategy implemented and the impact it may have on the cropping system, since the strategy of crop diversification is not the same at an economic or social level, as using mulch, for example. It should be also considered that measuring the autonomy of the farmer cannot be possible for an experimental crop, as happens with some of the crop units that will be studied in the AGROSUS. Indicator selection methods involving all stakeholders can be found in Lairez et al. (2020) and in Liu et al. (2011).

In summary:

- AS can be a viable alternative to conventional farming systems, since the environmental impact is considerably reduced in general terms, although how improve the economic impact still remains to be investigated. Finally, some conclusions to support the next stages of the research are also presented.
- Regarding the selection of indicators, especially economic and social ones, it is also advisable to refer to the literature on agroecology, where we find more appropriate measures such as the ratio between Value Added and the Gross Value of Production (VA/GVP).

- Most environmental indicators improve under agroecological weed management strategies. An exception is, in certain cases, the risk of soil erosion, due to mechanical weeding and later sowing date.
- Economic performance tends to decrease (usually slightly), especially in the first years, under alternative methodologies (Ruesch et al., 2022a, 2022b), although it can also be maintained. This is often due to reduced crop yields, as maximizing income is no longer the main objective (Becel et al., 2015; Giuliano et al., 2016). But this may also be because the results are not being measured with the indicators provided by agroecology, but through conventional profit measures. Some indicators, such as risk, are favoured when alternative systems involve diversification, although it also depends on the crop diversified (Salembier et al., 2016).
- Social indicators were either unchanged or slightly improved (e.g. workload and workload distribution and pesticide residues). However, the interpretation of the social criteria is rather ambiguous: there are those who consider a higher workload to be positive, because it leads to higher employment, and there are others who consider it to be negative.

4. Multicriteria assessment framework in AGROSUS

4.1. Objective

The main objective of this framework is to assess the **environmental and socio-economic impacts** of combined Agroecological Strategies (AS) in comparison with conventional use of synthetic herbicides for weed management, taking into account farms' profitability, to demonstrate that the proposed Agroecological approaches can contribute to reduce the use of synthetic herbicides while reducing environmental impact and production costs, but with higher socioeconomic added value, farmer wellbeing, environmental protection, and social and consumers' acceptance.

For this purpose, we developed a dedicated framework for the assessment of environmental, economic, and social impacts of practices based on Agroecological approaches for weed management.

4.2. The MCD method

A multicriteria model is composed of an objective or problem, and a number of alternatives that could address this objective, which will be selected by different criterion. In AGROSUS, the main output of the framework is the identification of the most adequate AS for weed management, or a combination of AS by crop and bioregion (alternatives). The criteria used for selecting the most adequate AS by biogeographic region will be the assessment indicators (environmental, economic and social, see the scheme of Figure 6). Consequently, the AS that obtain best value of the calculus based in indicators will be considered as the most adequate ones and a ranking of strategies will be also obtained.

Figure 6. AGROSUS Multicriteria scheme of the use of agroecological strategies (AS) for weed management.

A decision process will be carried out separately for each crop and pedoclimatic zone, once that all the bioregions and short-term and long-term experimental sites have been implemented by group decision options, if feasible.

Mathematical calculation of the value of each alternative will be done by the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). The outcome of the calculation will be the establishment of the order of preferences of all alternatives (AS) for each crop. Differences between pedoclimatic zones and long and short terms will be studied

Multicriteria Decision Making Methods (MCDM) were chosen because they allow to integrate the knowledge of experts, who can enrich the decision with their judgments regarding the decision-making problem. The most common drawback of existing multicriteria methods, at least for some classes of problems, is the need to translate the decision makers' knowledge about a decision problem into numbers and functions, as it could happens in this case, for example in social criterion. Consequently, the most convenient methodological choice is using models that can incorporate qualitative variables (descriptive, linguistic, or ordinal). Practical decision-making problems are often characterized by several no commensurable criteria, and there may be no solution satisfying all criteria simultaneously. Thus, the optimal solution would be a compromise solution according to the decisionmaker's preferences. The information is to be found in a set of labels, and the decision-maker expresses in a later step his/her intuition about the meaning of these linguistic terms. In this case, those responsible for the experimental sites could be the requested experts.

Any multi-criteria decision problem (MCDP) can be expressed by using the following five elements:

$$\{C, D, r, I, \prec\}$$

Where:

- $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_m\}$ is the set of m criteria that represent the tools which enable alternatives to be compared from a specific point of view, in this study we have considered the assessment indicators (environmental, economic and social) like criteria.
- $D = \{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_n\}$ is the set of feasible alternatives (agroecological strategies for weed management or a mix of AS) of the experimental sites, and from which the decision-maker must choose one in the future. In this case, the sets C and D are finite sets. This allows us to avoid convergence, integrability, and measurability problems.
- $r: D \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a function where a real interval corresponds to every decision d_i and to every criterion C_j .

$$(D_i, C_j) \rightarrow r(D_i, C_j) = r_{ij}$$

Once that the set of criteria and alternatives have been selected, then we need a measure of the effect produced by each alternative with respect to each criterion. By means of data collection of experimental sites and maybe by linguistic terms in some cases, if necessary, we can represent the goodness of an alternative obtaining indicators; the different values of r can be represented by means of a matrix called the Matrix of decision-making. A relation of preferences \prec by the decision maker. In this case, we shall suppose a coherent decision-maker; therefore, he shall try to maximize his profits or else minimize his losses to obtain the best alternative set. In some case the decision-maker could give linguistic information about the importance for each alternative. In this specific case, and by means of direct assignment, the importance for criteria could be obtained, being the valuation scale: Very low: 1; Low: 2; Medium-low: 3; Medium-high: 4; High: 5; Very high: 6.

Mathematical calculation of the aptitude of each alternative provided by the data collection of experimental sites will be done by the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). The TOPSIS technique is based upon the concept that the chosen alternative should have the shortest distance from the positive ideal solution (PIS) and the farthest from the negative ideal solution (NIS). The final ranking was obtained by means of the closeness index. In this study, calculations were carried out separately for each type of crop and bioregion within each group of case studies (defined in Table 1), to latter proceed with their aggregation to obtain a single value of the prioritization of the farming practices for each group of case studies (group decision). In this case, each type of AS was equally weighed in the group decision.

4.3. Crops and biogeographic regions

The crops to be studied in WP5, in which the best agroecological weed management strategies will be selected, have been described in MS6 (e.g., wheat for arable, vineyard for perennial, and tomato for horticultural). The description of Task 5.1 to consider 8-16 crops representing each of the agroecological strategy groups (cultural, physical and mechanical: biological and biotechnological and prevention based on digitization and technology) has been taken into

account. Similarly, 2 to 4 biogeographic regions using similar strategies on similar crops are encouraged to be collected, and the comparison between short and long term must be also considered.

For all this, the selected crops and biogeographic regions, and the AS chosen by the experimental site in the short and long term (Table 1) are presented below:

Table 1. Short and long-term experimental sites selected.

Type and crop	Biogeographic region	Partner	Biogeographic region	Partner
SHORT-TERM		LONG-TERM		
Arable Wheat	Atlantic	UVIGO		
	Boreal	EMU		
	Continental	PNU	Continental	PNU
	Continental	UAK	Continental	UAK
	Pannonian	SoE	Continental	ASS
Perennial Vineyard	Atlantic	UVIGO	Atlantic	UVIGO
	Macaronesian	UMA	Macaronesian	UMA
	Steppic	LAPAR		
Horticultural Tomato	Mediterranean	UPV	*	

*Horticultural crops cannot have long term

Crops have been graphically highlighted on the AGROSUS crop map (Figure 7):

Figure 7. AGROSUS experimental sites selected for multi-criteria assessment

4.4. Criterion selected

One of the main conditions for defining the criteria/indicators was that they could respond to the objective of the WP, that is, that they would be able to provide information on economic, social

and environmental differences of the different AS, in order to be able to choose the best AS for each crop and bioregion, to see the differences between adopting one or another AS for weed management.

Choosing a large number of indicators was not a viable solution, since most of them would not present differences between AS and would make it difficult to adopt this tool for future policy proposals. For all these reasons, key indicators have been selected for each of the groups of assessment criterion (economic, social and environmental), as long as data availability allows their calculation and the comparison among alternatives.

Economic indicator/criterion:

- **Profitability:** refers to the measure of financial return or benefit relative to the costs incurred. It essentially evaluates whether the benefits of an investment or project outweigh its costs and, if so, to what extent.
- **Viability:** in a financial point of view, this includes evaluating if the AS's benefits outweigh their costs, ensuring a positive Net Present Value (NPV) or Internal Rate of Return (IRR) above the cost of capital. Financial viability also looks at cash flow projections, return on investment (ROI), and profitability ratios. Finally, in an Operational Viability: This assesses the practical aspects of implementing the AS. It includes evaluating available technology, human resources, infrastructure, and logistical requirements.
- **Economic efficiency:** Economic efficiency is a key component of Cost-Benefit Analysis, focusing on maximizing the value generated from resources used in a project or investment. By evaluating metrics like the Benefit-Cost Ratio, Net Present Value, and Internal Rate of Return, we can assess whether a project or investment is using resources in the most effective way to achieve the best possible outcomes.
- **Investment's feasibility:** Investment feasibility assesses whether a project or investment can be realistically achieved given its technical, financial, and operational requirements. It involves analysing several factors to determine if the investment is viable and if the expected outcomes justify the resources and risks involved.
- **Life cycle costs (NVP):** Refer to the total cost of owning, operating, and maintaining an asset or project over its entire lifespan. LCC includes all costs from acquisition to disposal, providing a comprehensive view of the total economic burden associated with the project.
- **Economic dependence:** Economic dependence measures how reliant a community or entity is on specific economic activities or investments. This dependence can affect the economic stability and resilience of the stakeholders. In a CBA, understanding economic dependence helps to assess the broader impacts of a project or policy change on the local economy and its stakeholders.

Social indicator/criterion

- **Employment Contribution:** Refers to the total number of jobs created or supported by a project or policy, including direct, indirect, and induced employment. It also considers improvements in job quality, wages, and working conditions.

- **Job Opportunities:** The potential for new or improved employment prospects as a result of a project or policy. This includes opportunities for training, skill development, and career advancement.
- **Work overload:** Refers to the situation where employees have more work to complete than can be managed within a standard work schedule. This can lead to stress, burnout, and reduced job satisfaction, negatively impacting productivity and health.
- **Workload distribution:** The allocation of work tasks among employees in an organization or project. Effective distribution ensures that tasks are assigned fairly, considering employees' skills, capacities, and available resources.
- **Physical or operational difficulty:**
 - Physical Difficulty:** Refers to the tangible challenges associated with the physical environment or infrastructure that can affect the execution of a project. These challenges might include geographic, climatic, or environmental factors that hinder construction, implementation, or maintenance.
 - Operational Difficulty:** Relates to the challenges in managing, coordinating, and executing project activities effectively. This can include logistical challenges, resource constraints, technical complexities, or skill shortages.

Environmental indicator/criterion

The environmental indicators will be obtained of the LCA assessment following the ISO 14040 and 14044 standards. Consequently, the first step is defining the goal and scope of the assessment. The goal of the LCA is to assess the potential environmental impacts variations of the different weed management practices.

The limits of the study will be coherent with the scope of the project and will be fixed at farm level, setting a cradle-to-gate LCA. This could present some limitations, given that downstream life cycle stages are excluded. However, in this project, the products obtained are assumed to present the same quality (in terms of expiration, nutritional content, etc.) than the products currently produced. On the other hand, the crop yield is an important factor in the environmental impacts, and therefore will be included.

Inventory data will be modelled in specific software, and the environmental impacts will be calculated using a Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) method through classification and characterization of elementary flows. The methods recommended by the European Commission in the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) framework will be mainly used.

Initially, several environmental impact categories will be calculated (Table 2). Subsequently, those categories most suitable for comparison in weed management will be prioritized (for example, in addition to GHG emissions, ecotoxicity, etc.).

Once the above impact categories have been evaluated, it will be possible to estimate other eco-efficiency indicators. These indicators will be discussed at a later stage and will include the economic and environmental dimension. Also, the social dimension, based on the multi-criteria analysis.

Table 2. LCA impact category, indicators and unit.

Impact category	Indicator/criteria	Unit
Acidification	Accumulated exceedance (AE)	mol H ⁺ eq
Climate change	Global warming potential (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ eq
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	Comparative toxic unit for ecosystems (CTUe)	CTUe
Particulate matter	Impact on human health	Disease incidence
Eutrophication, marine	Fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment (N)	kg N eq
Eutrophication, freshwater	Fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (P)	kg P eq
Eutrophication, terrestrial	Accumulated exceedance (AE)	mol N eq
Human toxicity, cancer	Comparative toxic unit for humans (CTUh)	CTUh

4.5. Data collection

The data collection has been organized by the lead of Task 5.2 and was explained in the Milestone 7. In abstract: social, environmental, and economic data will be collected for the selected cases by partners responsible of those crops' field experiments in a provided excel database files for experimental site and agroecological strategy. Both quantitative and qualitative, data will be collected and safely stored in a single, central database to ensure data exchange between partners, tasks and work packages.

The Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) will be fed with data from the case studies and updated and regionalized agricultural LCA databases (Agribalyse, World Food Database, Ecoinvent v3.6, etc). A detailed technical description of current and new management practices will be developed in the case studies (WP5), which will be used to develop the environmental and economic data inventories.

Regarding economic data, the analysis focuses on the crop production data, which is strictly necessary for the analysis and is compatible with data from experimental activities, avoiding collecting economic data on the farm structure. Results can be later upgraded to approximate a value for farm profit by using existing data for standard indirect costs from scientific literature or economic databases, such as the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN).

Experimental activities focus on the impact of changes in specific farming practices (fertilization, pest control, tillage, etc.). If the available data are not disaggregated to a very detailed level, it might be difficult to integrate the information from the experimental activities. For example, the weed control cost savings from a given reduction in the amount of herbicide applied might not be proportional to that reduction, as other inputs participate in such operation (labour, machinery, fuel, etc.). Enough technical detail on all weed control operations would be required to assess such cost savings.

Consequently, the technical-economic characterization of the crops' production processes requires collecting detailed information on the different crop operations along the productive cycle. To that end, crop operations would be organised on a monthly basis, starting right after harvesting, and ending with the harvesting of the following crop season, and per type of

operations (ploughing, irrigation, fertilisation, weed and pest control, pruning, harvesting, etc.). Each farming operation can imply the use of labour and machinery, consumption of water and energy or the use of different materials. The data collected would be standardized to build a standard technical characterization of the production process for each crop, which would be defined by the different crop operations on a monthly basis.

Data to be collected on each crop's production process would therefore include: (1) quantity of production (crop yields); (2) use of inputs such as fertilisers, herbicides and other agrochemicals, energy and irrigation water (type of input, quantity applied, hours/number of applications, unitary price of inputs); (3) farm machinery used (type of machinery, crop operations, hours of use, fuel consumption, unitary prices, etc.); and (4) labour use (crop operations, working hours/days per operation, wages, etc.).

Bibliography

- Adamtey, N., Musyoka, M. W., Zundel, C., Cobo, J. G., Karanja, E., Fiaboe, K. K. M., Foster, D. (2016). Productivity, profitability and partial nutrient balance in maize-based conventional and organic farming systems in Kenya. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment* 235: 61–79.
- Adeux, G., Guinet, M., Courson, E., Lecaille, S., Munier-Jolain, N., Cordeau, S. (2022). Multicriteria assessment of conservation agriculture systems. *Frontiers in Agronomy*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fagro.2022.999960>
- Alaoui, A., Barão, L., Ferreira, C. S. S., Hessel, R. (2022). An Overview of Sustainability Assessment Frameworks in Agriculture. *Land*, 11(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11040537>
- Alletto, L., Vandewalle, A., Debaeke, P. (2022). Crop diversification improves cropping system sustainability: An 8-year on-farm experiment in South-Western France. *Agricultural Systems*, 200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2022.103433>
- Altieri, M. A. (1999). The ecological role of biodiversity in agroecosystems. *Agriculture, Ecosystems Environment*, 74(1-3), 19-31. DOI: 10.1016/S0167-8809(99)00028-6.
- Angevin, F., Fortino, G., Bockstaller, C., Pelzer, E., Messéan, A. (2017). Assessing the sustainability of crop production systems: Toward a common framework? *Crop Protection* 97: 18-27, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2016.11.018>.
- Aryal, J. P., Sapkota, T. B., Jat, M. L., Bishnoi, D. K. (2015). On-farm economic and environmental impact of zero-tillage wheat: A case of North-West India. *Experimental Agriculture*, 51(1): 1–16.
- Becel, C., Munier-Jolain, N. M., Nicolardot, B. (2015). Assessing nitrate leaching in cropping systems based on integrated weed management using the STICS soil-crop model. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF AGRONOMY*, 62, 46–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2014.09.005>
- Ben Abdallah, S., Elfkih, S., Suárez-Rey, E. M., Parra-López, C., Romero-Gómez, M. (2021). Evaluation of the environmental sustainability in the olive growing systems in Tunisia. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124526>
- Bloemhof-Ruwaard, J-M., Koudijs, H. G., Vis, J. C. (1995). Environmental impacts of fat blends. *Environ. Resour. Econ.* 6 (4):371–387. doi: 10.1007/bf00691820.
- Boardman, A. E., Greenberg, D. H., Vining, A. R., Weimer, D. L. (2018). *Cost-Benefit Analysis: Concepts and Practice*. Cambridge University Press. DOI: 10.1017/9781108241939.
- Caffi, T., Helsen, H.H.M., Rossi, V., Holb, I.J., Strassemeier, J., Buurma, J.S., Capowiez, Y., Simon, S., Alaphilippe, A. (2017). Multicriteria evaluation of innovative IPM systems in pome fruit in Europe. *Crop Protection* 97: 101-108, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2016.12.009>.
- Calleros-Islas, A. (2019). Sustainability assessment. An adaptive low-input tool applied to the management of agroecosystems in Mexico. *Ecological Indicators*, 105, 386–397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ECOLIND.2017.12.040>
- Cavan, N., Omon, B., Dubois, S., Toqué, C., Van Inghelandt, B., Queyrel, W., Colbach, N., Angevin, F. (2023). Model-based evaluation in terms of weed management and overall sustainability of

- cropping systems designed with three different approaches. *Agricultural Systems*, 208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2023.103637>
- Coteur, I., Wustenberghs, H., Debruyne, L., Lauwers, L., Marchand, F. (2020). How do current sustainability assessment tools support farmers' strategic decision making? *Ecological Indicators* 114: 106298, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.106298>.
- Craheix, D., Angevin, F., Doré, T., de Tourdonnet, S. (2016). Using a multicriteria assessment model to evaluate the sustainability of conservation agriculture at the cropping system level in France. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 76, 75–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2016.02.002>
- Craheix, D., Colnenne, C., Pelzer, E., Torres, N., Angevin, F. (2014). Design and assessment with farmers of innovative cropping systems to mitigate climate change and to meet sustainable requirements. 13th ESA Congress, 25-29 August 2014, Debrecen, Hungary.
- Crowder, D. W., Reganold, J. P. (2015). Financial competitiveness of organic agriculture on a global scale. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 112(24), 7611-7616. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1423674112.
- Cui, J., Sui, P., Wright, D. L., Wang, D., Yang, J., Lv, Z., Chen, Y. (2021). A revised integrated framework to evaluate the sustainability of given cropping systems. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 289. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125716>
- De Luca, A. I., Falcone, G., Stillitano, T., Iofrida, N., Strano, A., Gulisano, G. (2018). Evaluation of sustainable innovations in olive growing systems: A Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment case study in southern Italy. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 171, 1187–1202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.10.119>
- Deytieux, V., Munier-Jolain, N., Caneill, J. (2016). Assessing the sustainability of cropping systems in single- and multi-site studies. A review of methods. In *European Journal of Agronomy* (Vol. 72, pp. 107–126). Elsevier B.V. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2015.10.005>
- FAO (1988). Report of the FAO Council, 94th Session, 15-26 November 1988, Rome, <http://www.fao.org/3/t0087e/t0087e00.htm>.
- FAO (2013). SAFA Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture Systems. Guidelines, version 3.0. Food and Agriculture Organization, Rome, 253 p., <http://www.fao.org/nr/sustainability/sustainability-assessments-safa/en/>, last consulted 16/03/2021.
- FAO and ITPS (2015). Status of the World's Soil Resources (SWSR) –Main Report. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations and Intergovernmental Technical Panel on Soils, Rome, Italy, p. 650.
- Fernández-González C, Ollivier G, Bellon S (2021) Transdisciplinarity in agroecology: practices and perspectives in Europe. *Agroecol Sust Food Syst* 45:523–550. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21683565.2020.1842285>
- Finger R, Möhring N (2024) The emergence of pesticide-free crop production systems in Europe. *Nat Plants* 10:360–366. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41477-024-01650-x>
- Gaillard, G. (2016). Life Cycle Assessment of Agricultural Production Systems: Current Issues and Future Perspectives," *Int. Semin. Technol. Dev. Good Agric. Pract. Asia Ocean.*, no. May: 98–110.
- Galli F, Grando S, Adamson-Fiskovica A, et al (2020) How do small farms contribute to food and nutrition security? Linking European small farms, strategies and outcomes in territorial food systems. *Global Food Security*, Volume 26:100427 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2020.100427>
- Gasparatos A., Scolobig A. (2012). Choosing the most appropriate sustainability assessment tool. *Ecological Economics* 80: 1–7, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2012.05.005>
- geoFootprint. <https://geofootprint.com/> (accessed Oct. 06, 2020).
- Gerrard, C.L., Smith, L.G., Pearce, B., Padel, S., Hitchings, R., Measures, M., Cooper, N. (2012). Public Goods and Farming. In: Lichtfouse, E. (ed.) *Farming for Food and Water Security. Sustainable Agriculture Reviews*, vol 10. Springer, Dordrecht: 1-22, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-4500-1_1.
- Gésan-Guiziou, G., Alaphilippe, A., Aubin, J., Bockstaller, C., Boutrou, R., Buche, P., Collet, C., Girard, A., Martinet, V., Membré, J.-M., Sabbadin, R., Thiollet-Scholtus, M., van der Werf, H.M.G. (2020). Diversity and potentiality of multi-criteria decision analysis methods for agri-food research. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development* 40: 44, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-020-00650-3>
- Girardin P., Bockstaller C., Van der Werf H. (1999). Indicators: Tools to Evaluate the Environmental Impacts of Farming Systems. *Journal of Sustainable Agriculture* 13 (4): 5-21.

- https://doi.org/10.1300/J064v13n04_03.
- Gittinger, J. P. (1982). *Economic analysis of agricultural projects*. Johns Hopkins University Press. (No DOI available for this book, but it is widely cited in cost-benefit analysis literature).
- Giuliano, S., Ryan, M. R., Véricel, G., Rametti, G., Perdrieux, F., Justes, E., Alletto, L. (2016). Low-input cropping systems to reduce input dependency and environmental impacts in maize production: A multi-criteria assessment. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 76, 160–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2015.12.016>
- Gliessman, S. R. (2016). *Agroecology: The ecology of sustainable food systems*. CRC Press.
- Grenz, J., Thalmann, C., Stämpfli, A., Studer, C., Häni, F. (2009). RISE – a method for assessing the sustainability of agricultural production at farm level. *Rural Development News* 1/2009: 5-9.
- Hák, T., Moldan, B., Dahl, A.L. (2007). *Sustainability Indicators: A Scientific Assessment*. Scientific Committee on Problems of the Environment (SCOPE) Series, Book 67, Island Press, Washington DC, 448 p.
- Häni, F., Braga, F., Stämpfli, A., Keller, T., Fischer, M., Porsche, H. (2003). RISE: a tool for holistic sustainability assessment at the farm level. *IAMA International Food and Agribusiness Management Review*. 6(4):78-90.
- Hanley, N., Spash, C. L. (1993). *Cost-Benefit Analysis and the Environment*. Edward Elgar Publishing. (No DOI available for this book, but it is a key reference in environmental economics).
- Hardi, P., Zdan, T. (1997). *Assessing sustainable development: Principles in practice*, International Institute for Sustainable Development, Winnipeg, Canada.
- Hauschild, M.Z., Rosenbaum, R.K., Olsen, S.I. (2018). *Life cycle assessment*. Springer.
- Hawes, C., Young, M. W., Banks, G., Begg, G. S., Christie, A., Iannetta, P. P. M., Karley, A. J., Squire, G. R. (2019). Whole-systems analysis of environmental and economic sustainability in arable cropping systems: A case study. *Agronomy*, 9(8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy9080438>
- Hawkesford, M. J., et al. (2013). The role of agroecology in sustainable agricultural practices. *Field Crops Research*, 143, 55-61. DOI: 10.1016/j.fcr.2012.07.007
- Hurni H., Osman-Elasha B. (2009). Context, Conceptual Framework and Sustainability Indicators. In: IAASTD, *Agriculture at a crossroads, Global Report*. International Assessment of Agricultural Knowledge, Science and Technology for Development, Island Press, Washington: 1-56. ILCD, ILCD (2010) *ILCD handbook. General guide for Life Cycle Assessment -detailed guide*. JRC European Commission 2010 394 p
- Iocola, I., Angevin, F., Bockstaller, C., Catarino, R., Curran, M., Messéan, A., Schader, C., Stilmant, D., Van Stappen, F., Vanhove, P., Ahnemann, H., Berthomier, J., Colombo, L., Dara Guccione, G., Mérot, E., Palumbo, M., Virzi, N., Canali, S. 2020. An Actor-Oriented Multi-Criteria Assessment Framework to Support a Transition towards Sustainable Agricultural Systems Based on Crop Diversification. *Sustainability* 12: 5434, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12135434>.
- Jackson, L. E., Ramirez, I., Yokota, R., Fennimore, S. A., Koike, S. T., Henderson, D. M., Chaney, W.E., Calderon, F.J, Klonsky, K. (2004). On-farm assessment of organic matter and tillage management on vegetable yield, soil, weeds, pests, and economics in California. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment* 103(3): 443–463.
- Jannoyer, M. L., Le Bellec, F., Lavigne, C., Achard, R., Malézieux, E. (2011). Choosing cover crops to enhance ecological services in orchards: A multiple criteria and systemic approach applied to tropical areas. *Procedia Environmental Sciences*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proenv.2011.11.017>
- Jannoyer, M. L., Malézieux, E., Lafontaine, H. (2011). Are agroecological cropping systems suitable for tropical horticultural crops? *Acta Horticulturae*, 894. <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2011.894.13>
- Jose, S. (2009). Agroforestry for ecosystem services and environmental benefits: an overview. *Agroforestry Systems*, 76(1), 1-10. DOI: 10.1007/s10457-009-9229-7.
- Kates, R.W., Parris, T.M., Leiserowitz, A.A. (2005). What is sustainable development? Goals, indicators, values, and practice. *Environment: Science and Policy for Sustainable Development* 47: 8-21.
- Kumar, V., Jat, H. S., Sharma, P. C., Balwinder-Singh, Gathala, M. K., Malik, R. K., Kamboj, B.R., Yadav, A.K., Ladha, J.K., Raman, A., Sharma, D.K., McDonald, A. (2018). Can productivity and profitability be enhanced in intensively managed cereal systems while reducing the environmental footprint of production? Assessing sustainable intensification options in the breadbasket of India. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment* 252: 132–147.

- Lairez, J., Affholder, F., Scopel, E., Leudpanhane, B., Wery, J. (2023). Sustainability assessment of cropping systems: A field-based approach on family farms. Application to maize cultivation in Southeast Asia. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF AGRONOMY*, 143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2022.126716>
- Lairez, J., Jourdain, D., Lopez-Ridaura, S., Syfongxay, C., Affholder, F. (2023). Multicriteria assessment of alternative cropping systems at farm level. A case with maize on family farms of South East Asia. *Agricultural Systems*, 212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agry.2023.103777>
- Lairez, J., Lopez-Ridaura, S., Jourdain, D., Falconnier, G. N., Lienhard, P., Striffler, B., Syfongxay, C., Affholder, F. (2020). Context matters: Agronomic field monitoring and participatory research to identify criteria of farming system sustainability in South-East Asia. *Agricultural systems*, 182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agry.2020.102830>
- Lal, R. (2004). Soil carbon sequestration impacts on global climate change and food security. *Science*, 304(5677), 1623-1627. DOI: 10.1126/science.1097396.
- Le Bellec, F., Rajaud, A., Ozier-Lafontaine, H., Bockstaller, C., Malezieux, E. (2012). Evidence for farmers' active involvement in co-designing citrus cropping systems using an improved participatory method. *Agronomy for sustainable development*, 32(3), 703–714. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-011-0070-9>
- Leclere, M., Jeuffroy, M.-H., Butier, A., Chatain, C., Loyce, C. (2019). Controlling weeds in camelina with innovative herbicide-free crop management routes across various environments. *INDUSTRIAL CROPS AND PRODUCTS*, 140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2019.111605>
- Liu, S., Sheppard, A., Kriticos, D., Cook, D. (2011). Incorporating uncertainty and social values in managing invasive alien species: A deliberative multi-criteria evaluation approach. *Biological Invasions*, 13(10). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-011-0045-4>
- Liu, X., Charles, M., Bakshi, B.R. (2019). Including ecosystem services in life cycle assessment: Methodology and application to urban farms. *Procedia CIRP*, 80: 287–291. doi: 10.1016/j.procir.2018.12.004.
- Mayen, C. D., Balagtas, J. V., Alexander, C. E. (2010). Technology Adoption and Technical Efficiency: Organic and Conventional Dairy Farms in the United States. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 92(1): 181–195
- Méndez E, Bacon CM, Cohen R (2015) *Agroecology. A Transdisciplinary Participatory and Action-orientes Approach*. Taylor Francis Group, Boca Raton, Florida
- Meul, M., Van Passel, S., Nevens, F., Dessein, J., Rogge, E., Mulier, A., Van Hauwermeiren, A. (2008). MOTIFS: a monitoring tool for integrated farm sustainability. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development* 28(2): 321-332. <https://doi.org/10.1051/agro:2008001>.
- Mousavi-Avval, S. H., Rafiee, S., Sharifi, M., Hosseinpour, S., Notarnicola, B., Tassielli, G., Renzulli, P. A., Khanali, M. (2017). Use of LCA indicators to assess Iranian rapeseed production systems with different residue management practices. *Ecological Indicators*, 80, 31–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2017.04.045>
- Nemecek, T. (2013). Life Cycle Assessment of Agricultural Systems : Introduction. Present. LCA, no. October: 1–59. [Online]. Available: <http://www.agroscope.ch>
- Nemecek, T., Roesch, A., Bystricky, M., Jeanneret, P., Lansche, J., Stüssi, M., Gaillard, G. (2023). Swiss Agricultural Life Cycle Assessment: A method to assess the emissions and environmental impacts of agricultural systems and products. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-023-02255-w>
- Nicot R, Bellon S, Loconto A, Ollivier G (2018) The European networks of research, education and training stakeholders in agroecology. *Open Agric* 3:537–552. <https://doi.org/10.1515/opag-2018-0058>
- Oakdene Hollins 2011. EU Ecolabel for food and feed products – feasibility study, Feasibility Study of Oakdene Hollins, no. October, 2011.
- Oumer, A. M., Burton, M., Hailu, A., Mugeru, A. (2020). Sustainable agricultural intensification practices and cost efficiency in smallholder maize farms: Evidence from Ethiopia. *Agricultural Economics* 51(6): 841–856.
- Pannell, D. J. (2003). Uncertainty and adoption of sustainable farming systems. *The economics of sustainable farming systems*, 69-82. DOI: 10.1016/S0167-8809(02)00230-3.
- Pannell, D.J. (1999). Social and Economic Challenges in the Development of Complex Farming Systems. *Agroforestry Systems* 45 (1-3): 395-411.
- Payraudeau, S., van der Werf, H.M.G. (2005). Environmental impact assessment for a farming region: a review of methods. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment* 107: 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2004.12.012>.

- Pearce, D., Atkinson, G., Mourato, S. (2006). Cost-Benefit Analysis and the Environment: Recent Developments. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. DOI: 10.1787/9789264010055-en.
- Pelzer, E., Fortino, G., Bockstaller, C., Angevin, F., Lamine, C., Moonen, C., Vasileiadis, V., Guérin, D., Guichard, L., Reau, R., Messéan, A. (2012). Assessing innovative cropping systems with DEXiPM, a qualitative multi-criteria assessment tool derived from DEXi. *Ecological indicators* 18: 171-182, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2011.11.019>.
- Petit, S., Munier-Jolain, N., Bretagnolle, V., Bockstaller, C., Gaba, S., Cordeau, S., Lechenet, M., Mézière, D., Colbach, N. (2015). Ecological Intensification Through Pesticide Reduction: Weed Control, Weed Biodiversity and Sustainability in Arable Farming. *Environmental Management*, 56(5), 1078–1090. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-015-0554-5>
- Pope J., Bond A., Hugé J., Morrison-Saunders A. (2017). Reconceptualising sustainability assessment. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review* 62: 205-215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2016.11.002>.
- Pretty, J. N., Noble, A. D., Bossio, D., Dixon, J., Hine, R. E., Penning de Vries, F. W. T., Morison, J. I. L. (2006). Resource-conserving agriculture increases yields in developing countries. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 40(4), 1114-1119. DOI: 10.1021/es051670d.
- Rasul, G., Thapa, G. B. (2004). Sustainability of ecological and conventional agricultural systems in Bangladesh: An assessment based on environmental, economic and social perspectives. *Agricultural Systems* 79(3): 327–351.
- Reganold, J. P., Wachter, J. M. (2016). Organic agriculture in the twenty-first century. *Nature Plants*, 2, 15221. DOI: 10.1038/nplants.2015.221.
- Ruesch, J., Montrognon, Y., Labeyrie, B., Codini, M., Holstalnou, E., Drusch, S., Borg, J., Plenet, D., Gallia, V., Guiraud, M., Mouiren, C., Blanc, P. (2022a). EcoPêche 2: Conceive and evaluate innovative peach orchard management systems to reduce dependance on phytosanitary products.
- Ruesch, J., Montrognon, Y., Labeyrie, B., Codini, M., Holstalnou, E., Drusch, S., Borg, J., Plenet, D., Gallia, V., Guiraud, M., Mouiren, C., Blanc, P. (2022b). EcoPêche 2 project: conceive and evaluate innovative peach orchard management systems designed to reduce pesticide use by 80%. *Acta Horticulturae*, 1355. <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2022.1355.24>
- Sadok, W., Angevin, F., Bergez, J. E., Bockstaller, C., Colomb, B., Guichard, L., Reau, R., Messéan, A., Doré, T. (2009). MASC, a qualitative multi-attribute decision model for ex ante assessment of the sustainability of cropping systems. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 29(3), 447–461. <https://doi.org/10.1051/agro/2009006>
- Sala S., Ciuffo B., Nijkamp P. (2015). A systemic framework for sustainability assessment. *Ecological Economics* 119: 314–325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2015.09.015>.
- Salembier, C., Elverdin, J. H., Meynard, J. M. (2016). Tracking on-farm innovations to unearth alternatives to the dominant soybean-based system in the Argentinean Pampa. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 36(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-015-0343-9>
- Sartori, L., Basso, B., Bertocco, M., Oliviero, G. (2005). Energy use and economic evaluation of a three year crop rotation for conservation and organic farming in NE Italy. *Biosystems Engineering* 91(2): 245–256.
- Sattler, C., Nagel, U. J., Werner, A., Zander, P. (2010). Integrated assessment of agricultural production practices to enhance sustainable development in agricultural landscapes. *Ecological Indicators* 10(1): 49–61.
- Schader, C., Baumgart, L., Landert, J., Muller, A., Ssebunya, B., Blockeel, J., Weissshaidinger, R., Petrasek, R., Mészáros, D., Padel, S., Gerrard, C., Smith, L., Lindenthal, T., Niggli, U., Stolze, M. (2016). Using the Sustainability Monitoring and Assessment Routine (SMART) for the Systematic Analysis of Trade-Offs and Synergies between Sustainability Dimensions and Themes at Farm Level. *Sustainability* 2016, Vol. 8, Page 274, 8(3), 274. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU8030274>
- Schader, C., Curran, M., Heidenreich, A., Landert, J., Blockeel, J., Baumgart, L., Ssebunya, B., Moakes, S., Marton, S., Lazzarini, G., Niggli, U., Stolze, M. (2019). Accounting for uncertainty in multi-criteria sustainability assessments at the farm level: Improving the robustness of the SMART-Farm Tool. *Ecological Indicators*, 106, 105503. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ECOLIND.2019.105503>
- Schader, C., Grenz, J., Meier, M.S., Stolze, M. (2014). Scope and precision of sustainability assessment approaches to food systems. *Ecology and Society* 19: 42, <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-06866->

- 190342.
- Schimmelpfennig, D. (2018). Crop production costs, profits, and ecosystem stewardship with precision agriculture. *Journal of Agricultural and Applied Economics* 50(1): 81–103.
- Schindler, J., Graef, F., König, H.J., 2015. Methods to assess farming sustainability in developing countries. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development* 35 (3): 1043–1057,
- Soldi, A., Meza, M. J. A., Guareschi, M., Donati, M., Ortiz, A. I. (2019). Sustainability Assessment of Agricultural Systems in Paraguay: A Comparative Study Using FAO's SAFA Framework. *Sustainability* 2019, Vol. 11, Page 3745, 11(13), 3745. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU11133745>
- Šūmane S, Ortiz Miranda D, Pinto-Correia T, et al (2021) Supporting the role of small farms in the European regional food systems: What role for the science-policy interface? *Global Food Security* 28:100433 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2020.100433>
- Swinton, S.M., Lowenberg-DeBoer, J. (1998). Evaluating the profitability of site-specific farming. *Journal of Production Agriculture* 11(4): 439–446.
- Thiollet-Scholtus, M., Bockstaller, C. (2015). Using indicators to assess the environmental impacts of wine growing activity: The INDIGO® method. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 62, 13–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2014.09.001>
- Turner, J., Taylor, M. (1998). *Applied farm management*. 2nd edition. Blackwell Science, Oxford, UK.
- UNAIDS (2010). An introduction to indicators. *UNAIDS Monitoring and Evaluation Fundamentals*, Geneva, 100 p., https://www.unaids.org/sites/default/files/sub_landing/files/8_2-Intro-to-IndicatorsFMEF_2.pdf.
- Van Cauwenbergh, N., Biala, K., Biolders, C., Brouckaert, V., Franchois, L., Garcia Ciudad, V., Hermy, M., Mathijs, E., Muys, B., Reijnders, J., Sauvenier, X., Valckx, J., Vanclooster, M., Van der Veken, B., Wauters, E., Peeters, A. (2007). SAFE—A hierarchical framework for assessing the sustainability of agricultural systems. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 120(2–4), 229–242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.AGEE.2006.09.006>
- van der Werf, H., Petit, J. (2002). Evaluation of the environmental impact of agriculture at the farm level: a comparison and analysis of 12 indicator-based methods, *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 93:131-145.
- Vanclay, F. (2003). *International Principles For Social Impact Assessment*. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, 21(1), 5-12. DOI: 10.3152/147154603781766491.
- Vasileiadis, V. P., Dachbrodt-Saaydeh, S., Kudsk, P., Colnenne-David, C., Leprince, F., Holb, I. J., Kierzek, R., Furlan, L., Loddo, D., Melander, B., Jørgensen, L. N., Newton, A. C., Toque, C., van Dijk, W., Lefebvre, M., Benezit, M., Sattin, M. (2017). Sustainability of European winter wheat- and maize-based cropping systems: Economic, environmental and social ex-post assessment of conventional and IPM-based systems. *Crop Protection*, 97, 60–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2016.11.002>.
- Viguié, L., Cavan, N., Bockstaller, C., Cadoux, S., Corre-Hellou, G., Dubois, S., Duval, R., Keichinger, O., Toqué, C., Toupet de Cordoue, A. L., Angevin, F. (2021). Combining diversification practices to enhance the sustainability of conventional cropping systems. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2021.126279>
- WCED (1987). *Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development: Our Common Future*. (“Brundtland report”) World Commission on Environment and Development, <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/5987our-common-future.pdf>.
- Wezel, A, Jauneau J-C (2011) *Agroecology – Interpretations, approaches and their links to nature conservation, rural development and ecotourism*. In *Integrating Agriculture, Conservation and Ecotourism: Examples from the Field*. Springer, Dordrecht, pp. 1–25
- Wezel, A., et al. (2020). Agroecological practices for sustainable agriculture. *Advances in Agronomy*, 159, 149–209. DOI: 10.1016/bs.agron.2019.05.001
- Winter, E., Marton, S.M.R.R., Baumgart, L., Curran, M., Stolze, M., Schader C. (2020). Evaluating the Sustainability Performance of Typical Conventional and Certified Coffee Production Systems in Brazil and Ethiopia Based on Expert Judgements. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems* 4: 49. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2020.00049>.
- Wustenberghs, H., Coteur, I., Debruyne, L., Marchand, F. (2015). Pilot Activity 1.1.1 – Survey of Sustainability Assessment Methods: TempAg Network – Theme1: Delivering Resilient Agricultural Production Systems at Multiple Levels. Merelbeke, Belgium, 86 p., <https://tempag.net/documents/survey-of-sustainability-assessment-methods>,

- Yost, M. A., Kitchen, N. R., Sudduth, K. A., Massey, R. E., Sadler, E. J., Drummond, S. T., Volkmann, M. R. (2019). A long-term precision agriculture system sustains grain profitability. *Precision Agriculture* 20(6): 1177–1198.
- Zhang, Y., et al. (2021). Digital technologies in agriculture: Benefits and future directions. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 178, 105688. DOI: 10.1016/j.compag.2020.105688

